

Preliminary Study of Comparison of Safe Clearance Distances in Patient Beds According to the Anthropometric Structure of Anatolian People

Ferhat DELİBAŞ^{1*}

¹ Sivas Nitrocare R&D Center, Sivas

*Corresponding author: ferhat@nitrocare.com.tr

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Abstract

Comparison of safety and performance in patient beds according to human anthropometric values in Turkey. Safety and performance in patient beds are of great importance for the safe treatment processes of patients. In addition to the standards and regulations addressed in the safety and performance criteria, areas of use, product design and correct use also come to the fore. Since patient beds are devices that appeal to social use and whose user portfolio is constantly changing, the importance of safety and performance risk is of high importance. In addition, the legal capacity of the individuals using the patient bed, height, weight, old age and physical movement restrictions constitute the basic criteria in terms of safety and performance. It is important to determine the safety and performance criteria correctly. Risks for safety are evaluated in the light of appropriate tests and usage data for performance (Post-Market Clinical Follow-up “PMCF”, Post-Market Surveillance “PMS” and Clinical Data Evaluation “CDE”), allowing the real dimension of achieving high safety and performance to be seen. This article compares the standard of patient beds, the gap distances in their fixed parts, with the anthropometric values of Anatolian people. This evaluation only addresses the head, neck and torso compression risk areas of human limbs.

Keywords: Hospital bed, human anthropometry, safety and performance in hospital bed

1.Introduction

For electric patient beds used for adults, product design is carried out according to standards and regulations for safety and performance (TS EN 60601-2-52/A1:2011). Therefore, the priority for the safety and performance of patient beds is to address them in the design phase before the product is realized. In the second stage, the prototype is created and the safety and performance evaluation of the patient bed is carried out. Before the patient bed is presented to the market, the formation of the product is completed by performing validation, verification and qualification studies. In other words, we can call it the birth and development of the product. The section we will address among the activities carried out will be valid for only one section of the patient bed. This section is the safety-related sections that may pose a significant risk to the patient. These sections are shown as dots in Figure 1. These areas carry a significant risk of injury and death in the patient bed. We will compare the compliance of the Anatolian human anthropometric structure with the gap points specified in the standard (TS EN 60601-2-52/A1:2011). Since the area we will be addressing in the patient bed space sections will be related to safety, the safety and

performance of the patient bed are evaluated in the design phase depending on the factors that may pose a risk. These factors that make up the patient bed;

- Raw material components
- Mechanical working principle
- Clearance distances of moving and fixed sections
- Electrical safety
- Accessories composition and accents.

These factors affect the performance of the patient bed and also pose a risk in terms of safety due to faulty and non-standard applications. In addition, although the areas of use of patient beds vary depending on the user, safety precautions should be taken against possible risks (Wiggermann et al., 2019). The section we will discuss in this study will be the gap distance with a high risk level. There are three most important points that threaten human life during the use of the patient bed. These points are the head, neck and chest. These limbs of the human body pose a risk of death due to being squeezed into the gaps in the patient bed. It is of great importance to consider these points during the product design phase. The dimensions and weights of these limbs that make up the human body are factors in determining the risks. The probability of these limbs being squeezed on the patient bed is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Areas at risk of compression in the patient bed

The human body should not enter the gap distances in the figures below or should enter and exit easily. The aim here is to prevent the patient from getting stuck in the gap areas. The head, neck and chest limbs that make up the

human body are shown in Figure 2 in areas where there is a risk of being stuck in the patient bed (Hospital Bed System Dimensional and Assessment Guidance to Reduce Entrapment 2006).

Figure 2. Human image stuck in patient bed

The movements of the patient on the patient bed or the functional movements of the patient bed (Side rail movement, back angle movement, foot angle movement, lateral movement and Trendelenburg movement) increase the possibility of the patient's entrapment risk. These risks should be minimized to keep the patient's safety at a maximum level. The patient's safety should not be considered only as entrapment areas; other risk factors should also be evaluated. The minimum and maximum distance of the patient bed to the floor causes the patient's movement restriction, falls and the patient's risk of controlling himself (Morse et al., 2015; Wiggermann et al., 2017; Merryweather et al., 2015). Therefore, there are risks at different points in the patient bed used for adults. The

gap distances of the moving parts between the patient bed and the lying platform are also evaluated as risks. Here, we only considered the gap distances that pose a risk of head, neck and chest compression that will cause serious injury and fatal risk.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Evaluation of clearance distances in patient beds used for adults

The standard data used in the patient bed comes into play during the product design phase. The dimension values depending on the risk of head, neck and chest compression in the design of the product are given in Table 1 (TS EN 60601-2-52/A1:2011).

Table 1. Values determined by the electric patient bed standard for head, neck and chest regions (TS EN 60601-2-52/A1:2011)

	Value	Explanation
Head	120 mm dimension	Based on the fifth percentile head width of a Sri Lankan woman, measured from ear to ear over the face. Gaps smaller than 120 mm were chosen because they represent a conservative measure to reduce compression. The 120 mm dimension includes the entire reference for the fifth percentile of the smallest female head width and most of the international reference for the first percentile.
Neck	60 mm dimension	Based on the fifth percentile of the petite adult female neck. It should be noted that the petite person has a first percentile female neck diameter of 79 mm (fifth percentile = 83 mm). Factors such as neck compressibility, loss of muscle mass in the neck due to patient age, and asymmetrical shape of the neck support a conservative measurement of less than 60 mm.
Chest	318 mm dimension	Based on the ninety-fifth percentile of male chest depth. The clearances should be wide enough (greater than 318 mm) to allow the large chest to slide through without being compressed, to prevent chest compression.

In the product designed in Sivas Nitrocare R&D Center, the areas that may pose a risk of jamming were checked with apparatus. Figure 3 shows the checks with apparatus. Care is

taken to ensure that these apparatus have the dimensions and weight specified by the standard (TS EN 60601-2-52/A1:2011) (Table 2).

Figure 3. Control of risky areas on the patient bed that are prone to getting stuck, using an apparatus

2.2. The importance of limb weight in entrapment risk

The weight of the limbs (head, neck and chest) is of great importance when checking the areas that pose a risk of entrapment in the bed used for adults (Figure 1). Standard measurement devices have been determined for the measurement of the patient bed gap distances (TS EN 60601-2-52/A1:2011). Apart from the dimensional controls of these devices, their weight and angular values are also the most important criteria. The weight of these devices is determined based on the human limb

weight (Table 2). The importance of the weight of the devices performed for the controls here increases the risk of these dimensions expanding under any load, i.e. going beyond the accepted values, in addition to the gap dimensions found in the patient bed. For example, we can say the gap distance between the side rail of the patient bed and the mattress support platform. Because in any component and technique used in the mechanical assembly of the side rail and the mattress support platform, we can see the expansion of the standard gap values depending on the weight (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Example of compression between side rail and mattress support platform / Example of compression between two side rails

Due to this stretching, the risk of compression increases if the patient bed gap distances increase or decrease beyond the values specified in Table 1. The apparatus

values for gap controls determined by the standard (TS EN 60601-2-52/A1:2011) depending on the limb weight are given in Table 2.

Table 2 Apparatus and human limb equivalents used to control patient bed clearance distances

Control Apparatus	Length and diameter (mm)	Apparatus Weight (kg)	Human limb equivalent
Cylindrical Device	Length: 318 Ø60	3.34 kg ± 0.05kg	Neck diameter
	Long Area Length: 228±1 Short Area Length: 115±1		
Conical Device	Ø120 Ø60	5.13 kg ± 0.05kg	Head Width Ø120
Cylindrical Device	Boy: 318	3.34 kg ± 0.05kg	Chest Width

2.2.1 Assessment of head weight on the patient bed

The gaps in the fixed parts of the patient bed are Figure 1. In addition to the chest, neck and limb conditions, the weight data of the human

head is also important. Because the severity and probability of the risk vary according to the head structure. One of the important points affecting these risks is the human head structure. The dimensions of the head structure

and the weight of the head structure increase the risk of being squeezed into the gaps in the patient bed. An example is given in Figure 5. In light of this data, the standards determine the risk dimensions by evaluating the human anthropometric structure from general geographies. When the sources of the patient

bed standard used for adults are used, one of the studies related to the head structure is given below. The data from the Air Force Research Laboratory takes the size and weight of the human head as a source for the Joint Strike Fighter Ejection Seat Test. (AFRL-HE-WP-TR-2005-0044)

Figure 5. Risk of getting stuck between the side rail and the headboard platform due to head weight

Results of the Weibull distribution analysis for human head weight are listed. Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL-HE-WP-TR-2005-0044). The most vulnerable patient to compression, besides the size, weight and structure of the human head, are those who are mentally unstable and cannot control their body movements. These patients are usually very weak, elderly or unconscious (TS EN 60601-2-52/A1:2011). In addition, anthropometric dimensions emerge depending on the effects of the environmental conditions specific to the society. Different genetic structures in the human population are also the determining factor in the formation of these anthropometric dimensions (Güleç et al., 2005; Güleç et al., 2009; Özkoçak et al., 2019). Therefore, in addition to the human head structure, head weight increases the risk of compression.

2.3. Anthropometric values of anatolian people

When we evaluate the anthropometric data of adults evaluated in our country in terms of meeting the patient bed requirements specified in international standards, we evaluate the risk

level of the patient bed according to the data of Türkiye (Güleç et al., 2005). It is known that Turkey is also among the countries in the council in determining and preparing the standards. The applicability of these prepared standards for Turkey is of great importance for manufacturers and designers. Because the determined risk factors are not determined specifically for the geographical location or genetic status. The anthropometric data of Anatolian people were evaluated in two sections as women and men. Only the following main criteria were taken into consideration in the evaluation of this study. (Güleç et al., 2005)

- Head width
- Chest width
- Shoulder width
- Chest depth
- Neck circumference
- Head length
- Height
- Weight

These data are only data evaluated against head, neck and chest compressions.

3. Conclusion

The design of patient beds used for adults in terms of safety and performance is carried out in accordance with standards (TS EN 60601-2-52/A1:2011). In the light of the data regarding

the gap distances of the fixed parts in terms of safety specified in the standard, the comparison of the anthropometric structure of Anatolian people in accordance with these gap distances is given in Table 3 below.

Figure 6. Illustration of areas at risk of entrapment in the patient bed for male and female individuals

Table 3. Comparison of the anthropometric structure of Anatolian people according to the standard values of the gap distances of the fixed parts of the patient beds used for adults

	Average		EN 60601-2-52 Values	Evaluation
	Man ●	Woman ●		
Height	168.88 cm	155.03 cm		Suitable
Weight	74.74 kg	67.12 kg		
Head Section				
Head Width	155.68 mm	148.50 mm	<120	Suitable
Head Length	186.40 mm	176.77 mm		Suitable
Neck Section				
Neck Girth	376.59 mm	338.10 mm	<60	Suitable
Chest Section				
Shoulder Width	393.65 mm	361.10 mm	> 318	Suitable
Chest Width	293.48 mm	269.12 mm		Suitable
Chest Depth	212.53 mm	203.90 mm		Suitable

*The data were taken from the average anthropometric values of Anatolian people.

In the light of the data given in Table 2, the dimensional measurements of the head, neck and chest limbs of the anthropometric structure of the Anatolian people were evaluated (Güleç et al., 2015). It was observed that the standard values of the patient bed used for adults (TS EN 60601-2-52/A1: 2011) and the anthropometric structure of the Anatolian people were compatible with the space

distances of the fixed parts given in the standard.

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